

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: In the article, artificial intelligence and its role and importance in the digitalization of the economy are covered based on data.

Калит сўзлар: Artificial Intelligence, экономического развития, Intelligent Tech, Trade Initiative, «Интернета вещей».

According to the commonly used Wikipedia definition, “artificial intelligence (AI; Artificial Intelligence, AI) is (1) the science and technology of creating intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs; (2) the ability of intelligent systems to perform creative functions that are traditionally considered the prerogative of man. According to forecasts by experts from the National Research University Higher School of Economics, the volume of the artificial intelligence market (see figure) by 2025 will increase 150 times compared to 2016 and reach a value of 59.7 billion US dollars. AI will create 2.3 million jobs by 2020; by 2022, 20% of workers engaged in non-routine tasks will rely on AI assistance; by 2025, 85% of customer interactions will be managed by AI; By 2030, global GDP will grow by \$15.7 trillion.

The transition to the post-industrial phase of economic development and the building of an information society as part of the digitalization of the economy are primarily associated with the provision of services through digital ecosystems and platforms. Therefore, the assessment of the prospects for the use of breakthrough technologies, including artificial intelligence, is becoming even more relevant

today.

The main effects from the use of AI will be obtained by optimizing business processes and expanding the possibilities of automation and robotization of manual labor; restructuring of the global labor market and transformation of educational processes in favor of personalization and development of conceptual thinking; exclusion of subjectivity and irrationality in decision-making.

The widespread use of artificial intelligence to date is observed in the implementation of entrepreneurial activities. The wider capabilities of AI compared to traditional software allow companies to maintain a competitive market advantage. Software systems of artificial intelligence systems are able to eliminate a large share of human participation associated with their management through the use of big data, analytics and algorithms.

The main advantages of using AI algorithms, in particular in production processes, should be highlighted: - increasing the level of competitiveness of manufactured products by reducing costs associated with reducing outsourcing operations; - increasing labor productivity due to the automation of processes and procedures, as well as reducing the volume of manual labor; - Increasing the profitability of business activities by reducing downtime and reducing the total amount of capital investments.

According to a study conducted by the consulting company Capgemini, in 2019, 76% of economic agents associated with various technological processes implemented elements of artificial intelligence or are in the process of developing them. 37 In order to use the power of AI systems and the latest blockchain technologies to improve the effectiveness of international cooperation in the field of trade in 2018.

The International Chamber of Commerce and UNCTAD, within the framework of the adopted Intelligent Tech and Trade Initiative (ITTI), signed a number of agreements at the session on the application of smart technologies and trade tools. According to experts, computer modeling of trade negotiations scenarios using AI

will speed up the conclusion of commercial transactions, the quality of the development of international agreements, as well as the functioning of global supply chains.

In addition, AI services increase the efficiency of modeling the outcomes of multilateral negotiations. In 2017, based on the results of a survey of representatives of the banking sector, as well as key players in the public and private sectors of the economy, the Report of the Banking Commission of the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) was made, which outlined the main digital priorities for the participation of merchant bankers and the conditions for conducting export-import operations. The report concluded that 80% of international trade is funded by AI-sourced sources.

Traditional trade finance, which currently accounts for about 10% of all transactions, will show zero growth in the near future. The pace of digitalization of supply chain finance is expected to increase, mainly in the form of factoring. It is expected that paper-based document generation will be virtually eliminated, which will reduce the processing time of each transaction by at least 2 hours, which will reduce the cost of compliance procedures by up to 30%.

The adoption within the framework of the World Trade Organization (WTO) of a number of agreements on the facilitation of international trade procedures, the digital connection of merchant banks and the inclusion of cloud interfaces are the impetus for the digital transformation of the customs clearance of import-export transactions. Scientific research and AI implementations show how companies that use new AI capabilities make technological breakthroughs, gain tangible results and competitive advantage.

AI not only makes it possible to significantly modernize many technological and social processes, making them more efficient (increasing labor productivity and expanding human capabilities), it changes the very nature of labor, radically restructuring management processes and putting forward new requirements for a set of competencies, changing the nature of interaction between man and machine.

In our opinion, the most promising areas for the application of AI systems in the field of international trade are the following:

1. The use of artificial intelligence capabilities in building global value chains, which will undoubtedly have a positive impact on the development and management of global commodity distribution value chains, as well as improve the quality and reliability of forecasts, assess future trends in consumer demand and, as a result, increase the effectiveness of risk management.
 2. Development of international trade using digital ecosystems and social platforms. For example, today 97% of US small businesses export their products through eBay's digital platform. In addition, the inclusion of AI in the functioning of such platforms allows the provision of machine translation services for advertising texts, which, undoubtedly, is a driver for increasing international trade.
 3. Conducting trade negotiations and economic diplomacy, in particular the use of systems of intellectual and technical initiative. For example, AI algorithms can be used as part of the analysis of the economic requirements of partners in order to assess various conditions and assumptions, as well as directions for increasing the volume of export and import operations in various changes in market conditions.
- However, while identifying the positive consequences of using the capabilities of an artificial intelligence system in international cooperation, it is necessary to note a number of emerging serious problems and challenges.

The problem of the ambivalence of ensuring the confidentiality of information and increasing the availability of databases. The process of maintaining domestic privacy standards is a paramount factor in reducing the volume of cross-border transfer of personal data, which can negatively affect the development of AI algorithms. For example, the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) prohibits the transfer of data arrays to countries recognized by the European Commission as unreliable in legal terms. In addition, personal data may be used in the area for which this data was collected, and cannot be used as part of the deep

learning process of AI neural networks in order to improve the effectiveness of the methods of providing a particular service. Developing strict measures to protect the confidentiality of information requires the provision of a huge array of personal data for the study and training of artificial intelligence programs. And here the key problem is to develop privacy rules that do not create excessive restrictions on AI access to big data. The wider use of AI depends on a number of factors such as the development of digital technologies for the free flow of data across borders, advances in cloud computing, the generation and processing of big data, and the development of the Internet of Things.

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